

EFFECTIVENESS OF A CLASSROOM-BASED SOCIAL EMOTIONAL LEARNING (SEL) PROGRAM FOR MIDDLE SCHOOL STUDENTS

Mr. Dudhawade Dnyaneshwar R.

Research Scholar

Dr. Neelima N. Tikhe

Research Guide

Paper Received On: 20 JAN 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 24 FEB 2025

Published On: 01 MAR 2025

Abstract

The process of developing competencies of controlling and managing reactions helps students to evolve as responsible persons. This, in turn, minimizes the behavioral problems of students during the time spent at school or even in interactions outside school. The challenge facing schools is to establish education programmers that will stimulate social and emotional learning and integrate it with traditional academic learning to mitigate behavioral problems considered to be a significant impediment in the state of happiness and mental health of students. An affectionate and kind classroom environment helps children to feel protected and grow up to be healthy individuals who have a high moral standard. the social and emotional learning is the important process which is encourages the many life wining skills such as problem-solving skills, decision making, empathy, healthy relationship. The SEL develops the interpersonal and intrapersonal skills for maintaining healthy relationships to others. It increases positive behaviors and reduce the negative behaviors. It gives opportunity to develop social and self-skills and induces cognitive thinking

Keywords: *higher education; social and emotional learning*

1. Introduction

Education is the most influential weapon to bring about change in the world. It removes gender disparity, reduces poverty, creates a livable planet, stops unnecessary death and illness, a symbol of hope and confidence in the future of mankind.

-(Nelson Mandela, 2000).

Education must be considered in the context of its immense potential for bringing about transformation and social changes in the quality of human life. Its impact on bringing about paradigm change in the flow of social order can never be ignored.

- (Rath 2012).

The social & emotional learning project is nearing a critical moment. Depending in large part on what policy makers do next, it will either fulfill its potential to create a public good or it will fizzle.

- (McKown, 2017, p. 1)

Social-emotional learning (SEL) describes the mindsets, skills, attitudes, and feelings that help students succeed in schools, careers, and life, such as growth, and since of belonging at school. Educators use many names for this skill, such as “non-cognitive skills”, soft skills, 21st century skills, character strengths and whole child. SEL is an important part of a well-rounded education. Research shows that SEL is an important level for boosting academic achievement. When looking at SEL in schools, we encourage schools to focus improvement efforts on three general areas: student’s competence (skills), student’s support and environment, and teachers’ skills and perspectives.

It is important to mention here that researches in the field of social and emotional learning (SEL) has grown dramatically in recent years. That’s why educators should focus on promoting social and emotional competence. This will post student’s skills. The teacher’s role is to promote SEL because he is the engine of the class. Many researches revealed that SEL can be taught and measured that they promote positive development and reduce problem behavior and that they improve student’s academic performance, citizenship and health related behavior

2. Social Emotional Skills

Collaborative for Academic, social and emotional learning (CASEL) defined social and emotional skills as activities which helps children and adult in acquiring and effective application of knowledge, attitude and skill needed to handle emotions, to make responsible decision, to establish and maintain decision, to establish, attain positive goals, to realize & express empathy. Earlier Social-emotional learning (SEL) was considered a secondary skill but now it is reflected as an important tool to be successful in life. SEL consist extensive social and psychological skills which enable students to face challenges, handle emotions and communicate in better way. All these skills are the direct path to success in life.

Following are the Five competencies of social-emotional learning:

1. Self-awareness: It is the ability of an individual to consciously acknowledge the emotions and thoughts and what impact it is causing on one's behavior. In addition to this, it also refers to the capability of assessing their own strength and weakness and acquiring an optimistic and confident approach. It measures the following parameters: own emotions and thoughts; strength and weakness; confidence level; growth mindset/self-efficacy.

2. Self-management: It is the ability in which different emotions, thoughts and behavior is being managed in an effective manner by an individual. It focusses on areas such as handling stress, self-discipline, self-motivation, controlling impulses.

3. Social-awareness: It is the ability of an individual of being empathized and understanding towards other person's cultural diversity and perspectives, towards socially- ethically right behaviors, to respect the support & resources provided by family, school and the community.

4. Relationship skills: This skill focusses on the establishments of healthy relations with people of diverse backgrounds. This involves cooperation, active listening, proper communication, positive approach towards conflict negotiation.

5. Responsible decision-making: This competency deals with the skill of making judicious choices about one's own behavior and how they need to behave and interact with the society with respect to ethical standards, norms of the society and well-being of self as well as others. This also covers problem solving approach.

3.The importance of SEL:

SEL is critical to be a good student, citizen, and workers. Workforce demands aside, many call for the 21st century class- room to be student –centered and to support individual learning needs. Student's ability to learn well dependent on instruction, but also on factors such as the school climate, a sense of belonging with peers, positive relationship with educators and the feedback they receive. Neuroscience research demonstrated that emotion and cognition are connected; emotions are critical for all people to understand, organize & make connection between academic concepts (Usaki, 2018). To succeed in school, students need to be engaged, interest, and excited. They need to know how to focus on their attention on their work, keep trying, even when they face challenges. Working with others, effective learning, and communication are the key aspects of success. SEL promote positive development among students, improve academic achievement, and problem behaviors. Next, SEL creates a great motivation to learn and enhance academic performance. Early investments in ESL between children yield long-term dividends. In that they will avoid

Copyright © 2025, Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies

negative outcomes. Finally, SEL is related to other national youth development and prevention initiative, such as character education and school-based health promotion program. SEL provides educators with a common language & framework to organize their activities. Many programs related to children's' social and emotional development focus on a single problem to solve students' learning programs.

4.Promoting Socio-Emotional Learning (SEL):

A school, primarily, is an institution where children are grouped together for learning. This learning, however, should not just be academic but should bring children to a realization of what it is to be a human being. Thus, the main purpose of school should be the development of learners to live morally, creatively, and productively in society, The larger issues of education then should be to provide not only intellectual growth, but also to invest in social and emotional learning in children so that they grow up to be enlightened, benevolent, and accountable adults. Social and emotional competences enable the child to learn, accept, handle and communicate effectively the various emotional and social aspects of life. It teaches them to successfully regulate the work related to daily life, such as establishing positive relationships, social consideration, and exploring alternatives for solving problems.

5. Socio Emotional Learning and Quality Education:

The concern today is about providing quality education, which looks at the holistic development of the child, wherein the child attains his full potential and meaningfully contributes to and participates in society. Thus, the aim of quality education is to provide a pedagogically and developmentally sound education by which children can acquire attributes and skills to realize their full potential and become productive members of society. To meet the changing dynamics of the population, there is a need for not only promotes quality education at all levels, but also to provide equitable and increased access to it. Quality education is one of the major factors, which have the potential to increase the enrolment ratio, especially for backward classes, as it aims to foster skills and competencies to enable learners to support themselves and their families.

Quality education brings about the all-round development of a child, whereas SEL develops their readiness for learning with full enthusiasm, interest, and healthy mindset. Educating the whole child involves active, self-directed learning to acquire knowledge in a climate in which traits of collaboration and coordination are nurtured. These traits are deeply rooted in social and emotional learning. It strengthens the essential life skills of quality

education as cognitive development, high order thinking, integration that promotes intellectual skills, critical thinking, fraternity and citizenship respectively.

6. Role of Schools in Socio Emotional Learning

Educational leaders and educators can arrange activities based on SEL at the time of the morning assembly, when students collect as a community. For students who need more intensive treatment, educators can reinforce social and emotional skills by incorporating them in assembly activities and working with small groups of students. This gives teachers the scope to deal with individual variability, and promote student health and wellbeing, enabling students to lead positive lives. Students, on their part, practice and sharpen their skills by using them in various simulated situations.

SEL begins in the early stages of life, so it is important for its foundation to be laid while the child is in the care of the family. Going forward, SEL is promoted while the child enters school, and all through, till the time the child reaches the level of higher education. Research reveals that development of the emotion regulation ability in childhood is slow. After a prolonged period of immaturity, it culminates in maturity in the healthy and caring environment of the classroom. In the human brain's emotional development, this slow and prolonged period of maturing of the emotion regulation system or neural plasticity has proven to be beneficial for the neural system.

Conclusion

From the above discussion it clear that emotions are important in academic self-regulation and academic achievement of the learner. There is a need to develop the learner in such a way so that he can be able to create a balance between his emotional experience (positive or negative) and the situation. Apart from this, the teacher's emotional state is also influencing the emotional reactions of the students and vice versa. This emotional contagion can be advantageous or detrimental in nature. Hence, it is required that both teachers and students should learn to manage their emotions in different situations by acquiring different emotional management strategies.

REFERENCES

- PARAMJIT KAUR, & DR. MANOJ JHAJHARIA. (2013). TO STUDY THE EDUCATIONAL, EMOTIONAL AND SOCIAL PROBLEMS FACED BY CHILDREN OF WORKING MOTHERS . SHRI JAGDISH PRASAD JHABARMAL TIBREWALA UNIVERSITY.*
- JYOTI BHALLA. (2019). SELF REGULATED LEARNING STRATEGIES OF HIGHER EDUCATION STUDENTS IN RELATION TO CAUSAL ATTRIBUTION AND SELF EMOTIONAL MANAGEMENT. LOVELY FACULTY OF BUSINESS AND ARTS LOVELY PROFESSIONAL UNIVERSITY PUNJAB.*

Annu Kumari. (2020). EFFECT OF AN INSTRUCTIONAL PROGRAMME ON SOCIO-EMOTIONAL LEARNING OF ELEMENTARY STUDENTS SCHOOL OF EDUCATION. CENTRAL UNIVERSITY OF HARYANA.

Neha Goswami, & Dr. Rashee Singh. (2021). To study the Socio-emotional competencies of senior secondary school students in relation to social and emotional behavior, self-efficacy and mental well-being, Manav Rachna University.

Sivanantham R. (2015).EFFECT OF SOCIAL EMOTIONAL LEARNING ON CREATIVITY. Department of Education and Management TAMIL UNIVERSITY, THANJAVUR TAMILNADU, INDIA.